

CHANGE OF MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN THE PROCESS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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Abstract: The process of digital transformation is important in the modern business environment. This process is aimed at improving the efficiency and effectiveness of organizations through the introduction of digital technologies. Digital transformation also changes management strategies, as traditional approaches cannot meet the demands of the times. This article examines the change of management strategies in the process of digital transformation, their main components and practical examples. Through digital transformation, organizations will be able to increase their competitiveness, improve customer relations and take advantage of new market opportunities.

Keywords: Digital transformation, management strategies, innovation, technology, competitiveness, customer relations, organizations, change, strategic planning, market opportunities.

Introduction. Digital transformation is the process by which organizations change by introducing digital technologies and using them in their operations. This process requires not only technological changes, but also the renewal of management strategies. Digital transformation is essential in today's business environment to increase competitiveness, improve customer relationships and take advantage of new market opportunities.

Digital Transformation and Management Strategies:

In the process of digital transformation, management strategies change in the following main directions:

-Innovative approach: Digital transformation requires innovation. Organizations need to develop innovative strategies to introduce new technologies and use them effectively. This, in turn, leads to the creation of new products and services, as well as to the optimization of existing processes.

-Flexibility: During digital transformation, organizations need to increase their ability to adapt to rapidly changing market conditions. This, in turn, requires the use of approaches that allow for flexibility in the strategic planning process.

-Data-driven decision-making: Data-driven decision-making is critical in the digital transformation process. Organizations need to collect, analyze and

use data to define their strategies. This, in turn, helps to increase competitiveness.

-Customer relations: In the process of digital transformation, the strategy of customer relations will also change. Organizations need to use digital technologies to better understand customer needs and offer them personalized services. This helps to increase customer loyalty and attract new customers.

-Human resources and culture: Human resources and organizational culture also play an important role in the digital transformation process. Organizations need to change the culture to empower employees with digital skills and encourage innovative thinking. This, in turn, helps in the successful implementation of the digital transformation process.

Factors Affecting the Change of Management Strategies in the Digital Transformation Process

A number of factors influence the change of management strategies in the process of digital transformation:

-Technological development: New technologies such as artificial intelligence, big data, cloud computing and IoT (Internet of Things) will fundamentally change the way organizations operate. The use of these technologies requires updating management strategies.

-Changes in market demands: Changes in customer needs and market demands prompt organizations to develop new strategies. In the process of digital transformation, organizations need to improve customer relationships and offer services tailored to their needs.

-Changing competitive environment: In a competitive environment, organizations seek to improve their competitiveness through digital transformation. This, in turn, requires an update of management strategies.

-Social and economic factors: Social and economic changes, such as a pandemic or an economic crisis, affect the digital transformation process of organizations. These factors may lead to changes in management strategies.

The digital transformation process is essential in today's business environment. This process requires a change in management strategies. Organizations need to develop strategies that include innovative approaches, flexibility, data-driven decision making, improved customer relationships, and changing employee culture. When digital transformation is successfully implemented, organizations can operate more efficiently and innovatively. This process allows to increase competitiveness, meet customer needs and use new market opportunities.

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Conclusion. The process of digital transformation requires a change in management strategies. Instead of traditional approaches, organizations need to develop innovative and flexible strategies that support digital technologies. This process makes it possible to increase competitiveness, improve customer relations and use new market opportunities. When digital transformation is successfully implemented, organizations can operate more efficiently and innovatively.

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